

Prioritizing Science, Technology, and Mathematics Education (STME) for Sustainable Development in Emerging Economies: The Nigerian Example

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Abstract

This paper uses Nigeria as a case study to examine the pivotal role of Science, Technology, and Mathematics Education (STME) in driving sustainable development within emerging economies. It highlights how STME has historically underpinned human progress and remains integral to economic transformation, technological advancement, and self-reliance. Despite policy frameworks advocating for practical and skill-oriented education, Nigeria faces challenges such as inadequate funding, poorly equipped laboratories, outdated teaching methods, and a lack of qualified teachers. These issues hinder the effective implementation of STME and contribute to high unemployment rates among graduates. The paper calls for a re-engineering of the STME curriculum, emphasizing practical, hands-on approaches to foster creativity, critical thinking, and entrepreneurial skills. It underscores the importance of teacher training, attitudinal change, and increased investment as prerequisites for building a self-reliant and technologically empowered society. The study concludes that a robust, value-driven STME system is essential for achieving national development goals and bridging the gap between Nigeria and more advanced economies.

Keywords: Science Education, Technology Education, Sustainable Development, Self-Reliance, Curriculum Reform,

Introduction

Science, Technology and Mathematics Education (STME) are synonymous with the advancement of human civilization. Even before the advent of formal western education, it has sustained the progress of mankind in its crude form. In fact, the STM curriculum of today was drawn and modified from this crude form and has proven to be an indispensable tool in shaping world economy and sustaining same. The difference between advanced and developing economies is the application or deployment of STM curriculum in the educational sector. The will of government and policy makers drives this process and this is what is lacking in developing economies around the world. This however can be reversed with sustained effort by putting visionary leadership in place. This lies squarely in the hands of the people in a democratic dispensation. Priority has to be given to STM education, otherwise sustainable progress will be slow. Value change matters and we must know what we want and where we want to be, setting milestones for ourselves and shaping the future for our children.

Science Technology Mathematics (STEM) education impacts the relevant skills and training desired for sustained growth and development of any nation. Science Technology Education (STM) education leads to acquisition of consumer technology which every nation in a hurry to develop needs. This assertion is in line with the National Policy on Education of the Federal Government of Nigeria which stresses self-reliance (FRN, 2004). Most developing economies around the world equally have such policies as Nigeria.

At implementation however, gaps have been observed leading to the acquisition of insufficient or wrongly targeted skills. This is one reason streams of graduates roam the streets in search of white collar jobs which

are just not there. Well-adjusted STM education leads to self-employment which in turn has positive multiplier effects on society. This assertion has equally been made by Nwachukwu, (2009); Offorma, (2005).

The delivery of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education should be practical oriented, but it is theorized here in Nigeria because of lack of competent teachers or lack of equipment to enable hands-on demonstration. This one reason students graduate without adequate skills, and minds-on experience. This trend tends to obscure the relevance of STM education in the development of skills necessary for self-reliance. Such constructs as, curiosity, open mindedness, creativity, aptitude among others, are desirable when integrated with science, technology and mathematics. Mathematics also plays an important role in practical work and observation of nature as main source of scientific discoveries. Scientific discovery depends on critical thinking Sulai and Sulai, (2020). Mathematics is a skill developer. Seen as such, critical thinking develops skills, and skills build up viable economy. Mathematics therefore provides the vital underpinning of the knowledge of economy. It is essential in the physical sciences, technology, business, financial services and many areas of ICT desirable for economic transformation. Mathematics forms the basis of most scientific and industrial research and development (Adeniran and Odebola, 2017). The impact becomes visible and measurable. STM is generally used for a meta-discipline encompassing every training and skill acquisition underscored by this acronym. The entity known as STM education therefore offers students one of the best opportunities to acquire a life-changing education (Morrison, 2006).

Historical perspective

While science tries to explain things outlining the principles behind a every phenomenon,, technology translates it into usable and consumable form. It is the consumer form that you and I feel its impact and say 'life is good' (Mutasa in Nwachuku, 2009). Thus, the purpose of technology is the application of human knowledge for the betterment of human life. Hence, technology, therefore, seems to be a cultural activity and every society is technological and scientific in varying degrees. Looking at the advanced economies of the world, their success stories is unique and underpinned by their traditions and culture. China, Japan, India are good examples. Mathematics is the vehicle for doing science and a numeric tool for advancing technologies (Wasagu, 2009).

Researches have revealed that Africans of the Arab descent (Egyptians) developed Arithmetic, Algebra, Geometry, trigonometry and other advanced mathematical sciences (Diop, 1974). They employed these concepts in the construction of pyramid, mathematical calculations relating to the flooding of Nile, and in the division of land along the Nile valley. The Egyptians also possessed considerable knowledge of chemistry, and the use of metallic oxides as evident from the nature of colours applied to their glass and porcelain. They were even acquainted with the influence of acids upon colour (Sweeting and Edmond, 1989).

In the Nigerian context, several strides have been made by many people in the rural and urban areas where skilled men and women have produced the needed farming implements, local guns for hunting animals in the forests, machetes and hoes for clearing the land for agricultural activities. Even before the advent of western technology, our people already knew how to produced alcohol from fermented sugary beverages. Example is the one often labelled 'illicit' alcoholic drink. What makes it 'illicit? Is it because it is not produced according to western technology? Is western technology-brewed alcohol better than this so-called illicit gin? The answer is a resounding NO. Why can't this technology be exported? Must we always import when we have better local alternatives. This is where government and policy makers come in. They should provide the lead in harnessing our home-grown technology which is underscored by STM education, formally and informally.

The current situation and future of STM Education in Nigeria

Scholars, such as Oriafu, (2002) have argued that science, technology and mathematics education in Nigeria are grossly characterized by inadequacy of content and ineffective methodology by teachers, paucity of funds and facilities, equipment and materials in our laboratories, as well as socio-cultural limitations. These limitations have to be properly tackled for our STM education to produce individuals with sufficient skills capable of self-reliant life activities. The present trend of mass unemployment in Nigeria shows that the STM

education being taught in schools do not prepare our graduates to function well in a nation groping for a well-defined technological direction.

Self-Reliance as it relates to STM Education

One of the main objectives of the National Policy on Education (NPE) is the “acquisition of appropriate skills for a self-reliant nation”. Self-reliance is an expression which has become conceptually and practically attractive, particularly in developing countries, wrestling with the economic forces of meeting numerous needs with limited resources (Jimo, 2009). Though no nation can completely boast of self-sufficiency, but the zeal to bring out the best that is possible gives hope to all. With the apparent failure of regional and international governments, multinational corporations and even humanitarian organizations to achieve these goals, there is a resort to an inward looking tendency of self-help as a way out, after all, self-reliance as a form of social behaviour have existed throughout phases of human development (Oxfam, 2002).

Jimo, (2009) opined that STM education should prepare individuals for self-reliance and that this can be achieved by delivering STM education practically in such a way that it enables individuals acquire necessary and vital skills for self-employment. Fighting ignorance, alleviating poverty and resuscitating self-reliance is dependent on how well we take and embrace STM education. All these are prelude to self-sufficiency and employment generation which can be best achieved in Nigeria if STM education is taught as hands-on and minds-on activities in a practical manner in our public schools.

Challenges of STM Education in Nigeria that limits its Outcomes

These challenges include:

- Lack of funds to purchase equipment/materials
- Lack of adequate textbooks,
- Over-crowded classrooms/laboratories,
- Poor structured time-table,
- Lack of cooperation from administrators and even from parents,
- Inadequate monitoring and feedback mechanisms.
- Poor motivation to teachers,
- Obsolete/traditional teaching methods which ultimately hinder the internalization of learned materials,
- Poor policy implementation,
- Lack of qualified teachers,
- Haphazard planning

The Teacher and the STM Education Curriculum

The meaningful implementation and success of any STME curriculum for self-reliance rests heavily on the availability of the right teachers. (Wasagu, 2009). Nigeria has great human resource potential for all sectors, and many could be encouraged to embrace education, the teaching profession, trained, and equipped with practical skills and resource materials. Since the teacher is the translator, interpreter and trusted executor of the school curriculum in the classroom, then Nigerian STME teachers should be seen treated as the central figures in the meaningful realization of the program, as enshrined in the public school curriculum. The actualization of the goals and benefits of STME for self-reliance is a heavy task, highly demanding on the teacher (the implementer) and the school system.

The teacher is responsible for selecting the content, materials, strategies and pedagogies, preparation and presentation of the content to learners, evaluation and feedback. In addition, the teacher is faced with the task of constantly motivating and reinforcing the learners, as well as providing suitable socio-emotional atmosphere that is conducive for learning to achieve the desired goals. As such, they deserve special attention and motivation as this will bring out their best (Nwachukwu, 2009).

The teacher should be properly trained and must master a vast array of skills and competencies. Examples of such skills are knowledge of the subject content, capacity for practicals, minds-on and hands-on, pedagogical competencies, etc. Furthermore, teachers should view the learners as beginners; hence, they need to adopt practical approaches, such as using concrete examples and improvisations. Since the acquisition of skills necessary for self-reliance is all-encompassing, practical activities should be extended to simulations, games, etc.

Since no educational system or curriculum can rise above the quality of its teachers, it is pertinent that teachers should be trained with variety of pedagogical approaches which will facilitate acquisition of skills needed for self-employment and the corresponding effect would be self-reliance.

Conclusion

To say a re-engineered STME curriculum is desirable for the economic transformation of our nation is an understatement. No amount of public discourse on this subject can be sufficient to this effect. If all stakeholders, including you and I get committed to this reformation, we shall one day have a resemblance of an advanced economy. The overall objective is that of self-reliance and a better life.

Suggestions

- Parents and school administrators should give children and young individuals mental and attitudinal orientation. They should see STME as the way forward in an economy that is stagnated with insufficient white collar jobs to go around.
- Teachers should be properly trained on the STME curriculum on a continuous basis as new trends unfold. This is the only way to catch up with rest of the world
- Adequate funding is the deciding factor in the success of STME and should be a priority in government budgetary allocation.
- Laboratories and learning workshops should be adequately equipped
- Teachers should be adequately remunerated with a guaranteed future.
- For those who are already out of school, long vacation and weekend programmes should be organized in a non-formal setting to enable them to acquire self-reliant skills.
- There should be a shift of emphasis from certificate acquisition to practical skill training.

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